

Integration of linear thermoelectric modules composed of low and intermediate temperature p- and n-type metallic semiconductors into combustion chamber walls

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1 Introduction

In this study, an advanced design of the segmented linear TEG is proposed for the integration into a combustion engine system in unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) with two innovative integration designs: (a) T-shaped electrode based on a composite of Copper (Cu) and Aluminum nitride (AlN), and (b) self-joining by shrink-fit behavior of shape memory alloy (SMA). As the high temperature TE segments, bulk Mg₂Si of n-type and higher manganese silicide (HMS, MnSi_{2-x}, x=0.250-0.273) of p-type are used since they are light-weight, non-toxic and cost-effective TE compounds working at high temperature range. In the following, we will discuss linear-shaped TEG design and also its performance as compared with π -shaped TE module.

2 Linear TE module design

Normally electrodes in the linear TE design [1] were made by bulky T-shaped metals of Cu or stainless steel, where lower vertical block was only incorporated to pass electric current in a horizontal direction while the top horizontal portion of the T-shaped electrode played a role of absorbing heat energy from a heat source. The new concept of a T-shaped composite electrode is to replace the top metal block with AlN ceramic material which transfers heat from a heat source effectively to lower Cu block, and also prevents a short circuit between adjacent n-p pairs for AlN is thermally conductor, but insulator. Fig. 1 shows the prototype linear TE module we designed and assembled.

Fig. 1 Prototype linear TE module composed of p1-p2 and n1-n2 legs, which is submitted to high temperature (T_H) and cold temperature (T_C) through T-shape electrode made of AlN and Cu.

3. Experimental results

The measured TE generator (TEG) performance data are shown in Fig. 2 where the voltage and power of the linear TEG are plotted as a function of current, in Fig. 3 where specific power density and maximum power output are plotted as a function of temperature difference, $\Delta T = T_H - T_C$. In both figures, the agreement between the experiment and predictions by the analytical model are good.

Fig. 2 Voltage and current of the linear TE generator (TEG), experiment and analytical predictions which agree well to each other.

Fig. 3 Specific power density and maximum power output as a function of temperature difference, $\Delta T = T_H - T_C$ which are compared with the predictions by analytical model, resulting in a good agreement.

4. Integration of the linear TEG into combustion chamber wall made of Fe-SMA

The high temperature side T-electrode is integrated into the combustion chamber made of Fe-based shape memory alloy (Fe-SMA) for which we ran FEM analysis. It is found by the FEM analysis, Fig.

4 that the maximum shear stress of 439 MPa occurred at the interface of Fe-SMA and AlN part, which is much lower than that of linear TEG using bulk Cu electrode, and reduced by 42% compared with π -shaped TEG. More advanced linear TEG by using shrink-fit method gives rise to 47% and 9% reduced shear stress compared with π -shaped TEG and linear TEG without shrink-fitting, respectively.

Fig. 4 FEM model for the linear TEG integrated to the combustion chamber made of Fe-SMA.

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